

INFINITE

BUILDINGRENOVATION

Industrialised envelope solutions

D5.2

Stakeholder-centred value propositions and business models

Public Report

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D5.2 / Stakeholder-centred value propositions and business models

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About the project

Offsite prefabrication of multifunctional envelopes has been shown to be a technically viable approach to increase rate and quality of deep renovation of residential buildings. However, several barriers are still preventing a massive adoption of prefabricated solutions.

INFINITE aims at boosting the building renovation sector through the so-called "**Renovation4.0**" approach, which leverages on both digitalisation and industrialisation to offer **tailor-made solutions** with a high level of **design freedom, decrease retrofit costs and time** thanks to the optimisation of the value-chain and **foster the adoption of eco-compatible long-lasting products** and systems.

To do so, the INFINITE Project relies on three main pillars:

1. cross-fertilisation from digitalisation trends in other markets (i.e. Industry4.0),
2. exploitation of industrial capabilities and coupling with LC-thinking approach
3. experience gained from the 1st generation of multifunctional prefabricated envelopes

INFINITE promotes a life cycle approach that allows for comprehensive design, optimisation of the O&M and depletion of end-of-life residual value.

INFINITE partners cover the whole renovation value-chain. Together, they will develop a new generation of residential building renovation products and actions centred on the all-in-one industrialised Life-Cycle-based approach. Expected outputs include:

- a set of multi-user and **multidisciplinary design tools**,
- **process-optimised all-in-one industrialised eco envelope kits**,
- **adaptive control systems**,
- set of **demand- and industry-side matched business models** to show the Renovation4.0 market potential,
- a **structured framework of entities and knowledge** able to clearly and widely demonstrate the Renovation4.0 benefits.

INFINITE will unleash the potential of the renovation industry by increasing the market penetration of sustainable, high-quality and long-lasting building retrofitting products and methods. This will ultimately contribute to the decarbonisation of the European building stock.

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Executive Summary

The report focuses on identifying and pre-assessing stakeholder-centred business models to foster the market uptake of **Industrialized Deep Renovation (IDR)** solutions across the European residential sector. Anchored in the “Renovation 4.0” approach, it integrates industrialization, digitalization, and life-cycle thinking to shift the retrofit process from a traditional, fragmented workflow to a more scalable, product-based model.

The document outlines the **methodology** followed: starting with a literature review on renovation business models, it proceeds with the characterization of offsite prefabricated solutions and their potential users, culminating in the development of a **supply-demand matrix**. This matrix cross-analyzes user categories with technological kits to identify the most promising business model combinations, based on qualitative factors such as CAPex, OPex savings, incentives, and market perception.

From this evaluation, **three business models** were developed through Partners' interviews and workshops:

- **BUSINESS MODEL #1: Industrialized passive roof with Integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) + smart glazing window and adaptable building management system (aBMS) for Collective private users.**
Targeted at private apartment owners, this model enables energy self-production, enhanced comfort, and improved building aesthetics with relatively limited intervention. It offers flexibility in financing - either self-funded or via third-party investment (e.g., ESCOs or utility companies) - and can support participation in Renewable Energy Communities (RECs).
- **BUSINESS MODEL #2: Industrialized passive envelope with integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) and solar thermal (BIST) + energy and fresh air distribution and adaptable building management system (aBMS) for Public Social Housing organizations.**
Tailored to public entities managing large building portfolios, this model emphasizes process integration and prefabrication to reduce onsite disruption, ensure cost control, and improve energy performance. It can be delivered through EPCs or PPPs involving ESCOs and directly addresses the split incentive problem by exploring performance-based compensation.
- **BUSINESS MODEL #3: Industrialized passive and green envelope with integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) and adaptable building management system (aBMS) for Real Estate developers and investors.** Targeted at real estate owners, this model leverages aesthetic and environmental benefits (green image, higher property value) while supporting modular extensions like vertical rooftop add-ons. It appeals to investors seeking climate-aligned assets and can benefit from urban sustainability incentives and certification schemes (e.g., LEED, BREEAM).

Each case is accompanied by a business model Canvas, a qualitative analysis of the main benefits and an Insight Box describing suitable model's upgrades. These conceptual results will, then, be tested and quantified in the public Deliverable *D6.9 (Evaluation of INFINITE results implementation)*, applying each model to the real demo cases in Italy, France, and Slovenia for economic comparisons with respect to traditional renovation practices.

1. Introduction

Renovation is the procedure of returning a building to its original state or even improving its primary conception. At heart, the purpose of renovation projects is to lengthen the beneficial use of a standing building and as such it constitutes a cost-effective alternative to demolition and new construction. Retrofit, then, exists since ages, adopting different approaches and techniques with respect to specific historical and geographical conditions.

However, **renovation** intended not only as refurbishment and structural reinforcement but also as process to increase buildings' energy efficiency started in the 1970s when many Countries were shaken by the first fuel crisis of such magnitude. Indeed, the resulting increase in energy prices reflected on the need to minimize heat losses and the first external thermal insulation composite systems (ETICS) were installed on residential buildings.

Since then, renovation acquired more and more relevance, becoming a European priority from 2000 onwards, due to the urgent need of lowering CO2 emissions and limiting climate change: for the built environment, it meant working on façade and roof insulation, up-to-date ventilation systems and renewable sources for heating, cooling and hot water generation. To tackle the challenge of increasing buildings' deep renovation rate and quality, traditional approaches are no more able to keep the pace and new technically and economically viable models are under development.

Figure 1 Renovation 4.0 supply chain

The current digitalisation trends in multiple markets and the exploitation of the industrial capabilities within the construction sector, are the basis for disruptively change the retrofit sector, towards a full building stock decarbonisation. Hence, **Renovation 4.0** is a recent approach which aims at offsite production (every construction process which is done in a controlled indoor factory setting) of multifunctional envelopes, leveraging on digitalization industrialization and integration coupling (see

Figure 1). Even though prefabrication of retrofit components has shown several advantages (decreasing intervention time, higher quality, value-chain optimisation, life cycle approach, etc) still several barriers are preventing a massive adoption of such renovation method (high design efforts and investment costs, lack of hard-fact knowledge dissemination, traditional supply chains, etc.)

The main goal of this deliverable is the assessment of value propositions, within the framework of Renovation 4.0, that can improve the still-lagging market uptake of such innovative approach, requiring a shift from a project-oriented process to a more product-oriented one. **Business model (BM)** is the most used tool to describe what value is created from a certain product and what is the market segment that is willing to adopt it, with respect to traditional processes.

In this specific context, the BM's aim is to explore all the technical solutions developed within INFINITE project and, more generically, available on the market (supply) together with the potential users to be targeted (demand) and all other actors needed to make Industrialized Deep Renovation (IDR) a usual procedure (see *Figure 1*).

2. Concept and workflow

To reach the above-mentioned goal, the process followed within INFINITE project to select the business models is shown in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2 Workflow of business model definition

It starts with an overview of selected European projects and scientific literature tackling Renovation Business Models to underly the added and complementary values to be brought by this work (**Chapter 3**). Then, exploiting the know-how of INFINITE kits, the supply chain is analysed in terms of industrialized solutions' characterization and stakeholders needs (**Chapter 4**). Special attention is spent in finding the best integrated components which maximize the value proposition for a specific user category through a matrix methodology (**Chapter 5**). The core part is the development of three selected business models, which include a qualitative description, the valorisation of the related IDR benefits and one insight per each case that could enhance the described combination (**Chapter 6**). In conclusion, further developments are proposed to foster an iterative process with needed improvements towards more quantitative evaluations (**Chapter 7**).

For each step of the workflow, a series of activities were organized with project partners to obtain specific information about the market potential of the INFINITE kits (see **Annex** for the detailed description of each step).

3. Literature review

There are different projects and articles that have recently started dealing with business model innovation for renovation processes. **Table 1** summarises the most relevant documents that have been a source of inspiration for the INFINITE work, both in terms of methodology and contents.

Table 1 List of documents on Renovation business models

Title	Type of source	Main outcomes
<p>Prefab & Integrated renovation toolkits: an opportunity for social housing?</p> <p>Screening of business models for renovation toolkits</p>	<p>Heart H2020 project</p> <p>Source: https://www.housingeurope.eu/resource-1463/pre-fab-and-integrated-renovation-toolkits-an-opportunity-for-a-renovation-wave-in-social-housing</p>	<p>Success depends on integrating prefabricated kits into the broader building operation strategy (ventilation, heating, comfort). Social building stock is a good target for mass-customized renovations, due to its homogenous building typologies.</p>
<p>Sustainable business models for the deep renovation of buildings</p>	<p>Stunning H2020 project</p> <p>Source: https://renovation-hub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/STUNNING%20Final%20Publication.pdf</p>	<p>Deep renovation works best when incentives are clearly integrated with technical offerings (e.g., performance warranties, EPC) and are provided by a unique entity, such as the One-Stop-Shop (OSS). Funding facilitation and intermediation needs to be embedded into business models.</p>
<p>Business models for rolling out Positive Energy Buildings</p>	<p>Earth and Environmental Science article</p> <p>Source: https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/1122/1/012060/pdf</p>	<p>Positive energy solutions offer multiple value streams (energy sale, community benefit). Optional modules enabling energy community participation should be considered in the business model, focusing on flexibility and user empowerment.</p>
<p>Renovating the retrofit process: People-centred business models and co-created partnerships for low-energy buildings in Norway</p>	<p>Energy Research & Social Science article</p> <p>Source: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S221462962100493X</p>	<p>Co-creation with users is crucial for adoption of renovation practices. Business model development should foresee active engagement and post-installation services, not just product delivery.</p>
<p>Boosting energy home renovation through innovative business models: ONE-STOP-SHOP solutions assessment</p>	<p>Journal of Cleaner Production article</p> <p>Source: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0959652621041585</p>	<p>Successful OSS models create trust through transparency and performance monitoring. It's important to always integrate real-time performance feedback (through BMS and monitoring tools).</p>

<p>In the pursuit of sustainable building renovation: strategic partnerships and new business models in construction</p>	<p>DTU PhD thesis</p> <p>Source: https://backend.orbit.dtu.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/316116117/Jakob_Brink_Berg.pdf</p>	<p>Strategic cross-sector partnerships (e.g., real estate funds + energy service companies + prefab manufacturers) are key to scaling. Renovation business models must systematically align and consider all involved stakeholders.</p>
<p>Exploitation of Business Models for Deep Renovation</p>	<p>MDPI Proceedings of Sustainable Places 2019</p> <p>Source: https://www.mdpi.com/2504-3900/20/1/11</p>	<p>Integrated retrofit kits must be considered not just as technical products, but as strategic investment tools with quantifiable risk reduction, resilience, and energy savings, especially appealing to asset managers of large, vulnerable housing stocks. Such integration can be gathered in online platforms offering full renovation journey experiences.</p>
<p>New Business Models for Industrialized Construction</p>	<p>Industry 4.0 for the Built Environment article</p> <p>Source: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356747882_New_Business_Models_for_Industrialized_Construction</p>	<p>Industrialized renovation demands new business model archetypes that break away from traditional, fragmented value chains, focusing instead on vertical integration, digitalization, and productization. In addition, new value capture mechanisms (e.g., leasing components, performance guarantees, energy savings) are key to making prefabricated solutions viable.</p>
<p>Collaborative business model development for home energy renovations</p>	<p>Energy Efficiency article</p> <p>Source: https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12053-018-9663-3</p>	<p>Key success factors for renovation projects are multi-actor coordination, demand aggregation, and tailored customer segmentation. For effective business models, dealing with complex stakeholder value chains, it's important to integrate technical, financial, and service layers.</p>

From the above-mentioned documents it clearly emerges that, innovation in renovation business model is a discussed and up-to-date topic, both in literature and in European projects. On one hand, focus is given to the involvement of the whole supply-chain, from one-stop-shops to new partnerships and final users. On the other hand, attention goes also to the achievement of deep retrofit and nZEB performances.

However, **industrialization** is rarely mentioned in terms of needed paradigm shift with respect to traditional interventions and it's addressed mostly for new construction projects. The goal of this report is, to highlight and quantify the benefits brought by Renovation 4.0 to overcome barriers (which are currently seen as prevailing by the market) and valorise the developed business models.

4. Supply chain characterization

Starting with the data and information gathered in INFINITE project (mainly on the development of innovative technologies but also on the analysis of the Renovation 4.0 market potential), a relevant list of **IDR solutions** and **user categories** have been collected (see *Annex A.1*) and described in the following paragraphs.

IDR solutions

From the supply side, the industrialized solutions that can be combined and integrated offsite, according to the stakeholders' needs, are the one listed and described in *Table 2*.

Table 2 Description of IDR solutions

IDR SOLUTION	DESCRIPTION	PROs	CONS
Industrialized passive envelope 	Prefabricated façade or roof modules with integrated insulation and finishing, designed for fast, standardized installation. It supports offsite construction and reduced onsite labor.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Faster installation – High factory-quality and industrial scalability – Guaranteed insulation and energy savings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High initial CAPex – Design limitations for complex geometries – Structural compatibility required
Passive and green envelope 	Envelope modules combining insulation and vegetation layers (e.g., climbing plants, or structured gardens), enhancing energy and environmental performance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Urban cooling and acoustic insulation – Enhanced biodiversity – Aesthetic and market value boost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High maintenance (irrigation, trimming) – Increased structural load – Risk of leaks or pests
Energy and fresh air distribution 	Ventilation modules integrating air intake, heat recovery, and sometimes heating/cooling generation, enabling healthier indoor environments. It can be placed directly in the passive façade module or on the balcony's rail.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Improved air quality and comfort – Reduced indoor humidity and mold risk – Decentralized air handling for single apartments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High initial cost – Careful integration required – Perceived complexity by users
Adaptable Building Management System (aBMS) 	Digital system monitoring and controlling building energy flows (heating, lighting, ventilation, etc.) with real-time feedback to the building users or managers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Smart energy use – Easy maintenance planning – Support to EPC and performance guarantees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Costly licenses – Need of skilled operators – Interoperability challenges

<p>Building integrated photovoltaics (BIPV)</p>	<p>PV modules integrated into the building skin (façade or roof), replacing conventional cladding or roofing materials while generating electricity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Dual functionality (power and finishing) – Aesthetic integration with passive cladding – Local energy generation and net metering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Higher cost than classic rooftop PV – Limited solar exposure on façades – Complex installation logistics
<p>Building integrated solar thermal (BIST)</p>	<p>Solar thermal collectors embedded in façades or roofs for domestic hot water and heating. The solution can also act as a cooling system where the panels are used as evaporators.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reduced heating demand – Dual functionality (heating and finishing) – High energy efficiency (thanks to adaptive controller) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Low output in winter (when demand is high) – Aesthetic and design limitations – Low modularity and complex maintenance.
<p>Smart glazing window</p>	<p>Windows with embedded sensors and coatings that regulate heat gain, daylighting, and glare, often connected to aBMS for adaptive control.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Improved thermal comfort – Remote control – Enhanced aesthetics and daylighting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High initial cost – Reliability and maintenance of sensors – Limited benefit in coldclimates

It is worth mentioning that the offsite technological kits listed above were all developed and tested as part of the INFINITE project (which helped to provide useful benchmarking data). However, each category can be also Intended as generic, including a range of possible innovative technological components (coming from different manufacturers, using different construction materials or technical systems, etc.).

Moreover, even if technologies are listed separately, to achieve the ambitious decarbonization goals set forth by the European Union, it is essential to **integrate and combine various Industrialized Deep Renovation (IDR) solutions**. By doing so, it's possible to maximize energy savings, enhance building performance, and significantly reduce carbon emissions. Business models should, then, focus on finding the optimal cost-benefit combination of these solutions - according to the user's needs- to ensure that financial investments are justified by the environmental, social and economic benefits.

Finally, looking at the whole spectrum, before focusing on specific users' categories needs, it's worth mentioning that there are some **ideal building prerequisites** for conducting industrialized deep renovations (see *Deliverable D2.1: Building stock analysis to support industrialized deep retrofit*). Indeed, some solutions could really fit certain potential user needs but could not be applicable to a given stock. After having defined the promising business model, then, a technical feasibility study is needed to assess the potential of industrialization of a given portfolio. Furthermore, it is essential to consider the different national contexts which influence the technology selection and combinations, making the business models country-specific, besides the general common considerations presented in this report.

User categories

Moving to the **demand side**, the focus of INFINITE business models is oriented to residential property structures, but it can easily be adapted to other sectors such as commercial or tertiary portfolios, especially for Real Estate actors. Indeed, prioritizing residential buildings for deep renovation in the EU is crucial, because they account for a significant portion of energy consumption and emissions (around 40%). Focusing on these buildings can deliver substantial environmental, social, and economic benefits, including improved living conditions, reduced energy bills, and increased property values. This focus also aligns with EU policies and targets, making residential buildings a key priority for achieving decarbonization goals.

END-USERS

Given such premise, the following end-users and key stakeholders of INFINITE IDR solutions, have been identified:

Single private user:

A single private user refers to an individual or entity who owns a specific property and holds sole responsibility for its management and decision-making related to retrofitting. This stakeholder is typically not a public or government entity but rather a private individual, company, or organization. These stakeholders play a crucial role in the property industry as they have the authority to make lean investment decisions regarding energy efficiency, sustainability, or functionality.

Collective private user:

A collective private user refers to a group of individuals or entities who jointly own a building block, a condominium or multi-unit property and collaborate in decision-making regarding retrofitting initiatives. These stakeholders typically represent the collective interests of the residents and are responsible for overseeing property improvements. These collective private users often form condominium or other type of associations to collectively address building management matters. Common agreements are usually needed for operations of extraordinary maintenance, such as renovations.

Public Social Housing organizations:

Public social housing organizations refer to government entities responsible for the ownership, management, and provision of social housing to low-income or disadvantaged populations. Public owners in this context typically agencies at the regional or local level, which own and operate housing units or complexes intended to address housing needs within the community. Public housing organizations are characterized but a single ownership or management structure, but they need to satisfy the needs of their tenants, who are the beneficiary of part of the retrofit benefits (such as better comfort and lower energy bills).

Private Social Housing organizations:

Private social housing organizations are non-governmental entities with a private ownership structure that operate in the realm of social housing. These organizations provide affordable housing options to individuals and families with limited financial resources to bridge the gap between the demand for affordable housing and the availability of public units in the market. The most typical model is the Cooperative one. Members purchase shares in the cooperative, granting them the right to occupy a unit and participate in decision-making processes. This model promotes long-term affordability, democratic governance, and community engagement.

Real estate developers and investors:

Real estate developers and investors are companies that own, operate, or finance income-producing real estate assets. They invest in a diverse range of properties and typically generate income through rental or capital gains from property sales. They can be investment funds (among which pension, endowments, or insurance companies) when they pool capital from multiple investors to acquire, develop, or manage a building portfolio. Developers, instead, are entities involved in the construction and development of new real estate projects. They also participate in retrofit solutions, especially when refurbishing existing properties to meet modern standards and requirements. When considering renovation solutions, Real Estate entities focus on minimizing the risk, enhancing the long-term value, reducing operating costs and optimizing the income potential of their portfolios by improving energy efficiency, sustainability, and overall property performance.

INTERMEDIARIES

In addition to end-users, another important category to consider are intermediaries which play a pivotal role in bridging the gap between **technology providers** and **end-users**. These actors — including **general contractors**, **ESCOs**, **One-Stop-Shops (OSS)**, **third-party investors**, and **facility managers** — are critical enablers of integrated, large-scale renovation projects. Their influence extends beyond execution: they shape procurement models, financing mechanisms, and user trust in offsite industrialized solutions. The main categories are:

General Contractors

General contractors oversee the entire renovation workflow — from design to execution — and are vital in managing the integration of prefabricated kits (e.g. INFINITE's passive façades, ventilation modules and BIPV systems). They coordinate subcontractors, scheduling, regulatory compliance and safety standards. As construction timelines tighten and quality expectations rise, general contractors are increasingly drawn to offsite approaches for their ability to reduce risk, shorten site time, and deliver predictable outcomes.

Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)

ESCOs offer performance-based renovation services, often through Energy Performance Contracts (EPCs) that guarantee energy savings. This makes them ideal intermediaries for deep renovation projects where upfront costs are a barrier. Industrialized solutions like INFINITE's — with reliable, replicable performance metrics — are well-suited for EPCs, as they enable predictable savings

calculations and long-term maintenance bundling. ESCOs are particularly strategic when working with public housing or large portfolios, where they absorb financial and technical risks while ensuring measurable results (see *Insight box #2* for further details).

One-Stop-Shops (OSS)

OSS entities aim to simplify renovation journeys by offering turnkey solutions — covering design, financing advice, permitting, coordination, and aftercare. For residential users (especially condominiums or private collectives), OSS actors are crucial to de-risk complex interventions. INFINITE's modular and mass-customizable kits approach with OSS delivery models, allowing them to offer streamlined renovation packages with clear cost/time estimates, standardized guarantees, and post-installation monitoring — all of which are key to customer trust and market uptake.

Third-Party Investors

These actors (e.g. impact investors, infrastructure funds, green bonds issuers) provide capital to cover the upfront costs of retrofits in return for a share of the future savings or value increase. They are increasingly drawn to standardized, scalable solutions like INFINITE's ones, which reduce delivery risk and enable portfolio-based investment strategies. Their participation is often tied to the availability of performance data, warranties, and clear legal frameworks, all of which are strengthened by prefabricated and monitored interventions.

Facility managers

Especially relevant for real estate funds and large owners, facilities managers oversee long-term building performance. Their inclusion ensures that industrialized components — with their higher durability — are properly operated and maintained. Their feedback also informs design for maintainability, a core tenet of INFINITE kits' life-cycle-oriented innovation.

Overall, all Intermediaries' categories **seem to be potentially interested in INFINITE's Industrialized kits approach to renovation**, since it offers flexibility in the range of possible combinations, all associated to warranties, performance verification, and post-renovation services (crucial aspects to gain end-users trust). Embedding these actors early in the business model development strengthens the replicability and commercial viability of the renovation offer across diverse market segments. For this reason, intermediaries have not been included in the matrix since their role and cost-benefit ratio needs to be assessed for each specific case study.

5. Supply – demand matrix tool

To demonstrate the market potential of INFINITE Renovation 4.0 approach, the definition of the most promising business models is a crucial and delicate step. Through an online workshop (see *Annex A.1*) it has, then, been created a **matrix to match the available IDR solutions** (supply) **with the potential User categories** who could apply them to their building stock (demand). Special attention is spent in integrating the kits to maximize the value proposition for a specific stakeholder.

Given the availability of a diverse range of supply and demand categories, the matrix structure (see *Table 3*) has been organized and represented as follow:

- **Columns** = list of Renovation 4.0 solutions and kits, addressed individually but also considered from a fully or partially integrated point of view;
- **Rows** = list of potential users and stakeholders interested in the value proposition of the identified retrofit solutions;
- **Cells** = Qualitative business model assessment to estimate the market potential of the different kits with respect to a specific stakeholder category.

The **qualitative evaluation of each cell** of the matrix is made taking into consideration the following business model factors:

1. Incentives availability (I)

An incentive is a federal, state, or local government measure that is intended to encourage individuals and businesses to spend money and to attract new capital investment in a given sector/industry. They are Country specific, and they can take many forms: cash grants, tax credits, tax exemptions/abatements/rebates, forgivable loans, low interest financing etc. Usually, they are tied to certain renovation expenses related to energy efficiency or anti-seismic improvements and an extra reward for offsite solutions is rarely applied.

2. Payback from OPex savings (O)

OPex are operating expenses so costs which incur for running day-to-day operations. After a renovation intervention, savings from OPex are intended as all the cost reductions coming from lower energy bills, fewer ordinary/extraordinary maintenance but also incomes generated from photovoltaic panels. OPex savings are strictly dependent on the product/kit performances, specifications and guarantees over time. Precise data should be collected from the solution providers.

3. Savings from CAPex reduction (C)

CAPex are capital expenditures so major investments which occur from time to time with a long-term purpose and duration. Considering an industrialized renovation intervention, that is a major investment, CAPex savings are calculated with respect to the traditional approach. In fact, they are related to the increased efficiency of offsite works, the time reduction of onsite works, the system integration of components, the process disintermediation and so on. Precise data should be collected

from a deep analysis of the overall supply chain, considering that significant savings will start only when economies of scale and learning will kick-in.

4. Recognized market value (M)

It's the qualitative value that a specific stakeholder/user recognizes in the adoption of a renovation product/kit. It considers both the benefits and disadvantages coming from the solution's features and performances, such as healthier environment, increased safety and comfort, improved acoustic insulation, reduced energy costs, etc. In a broader sense, it can include also the indirect social and environmental impacts deriving from the Industrialized renovation intervention, even though they are still hard to be monetized. Some examples are the decarbonization potential related to the reduced CO2 emissions or social externalities linked to lowered energy poverty and regeneration processes.

For every cell, the presence of the above-mentioned positive factors can be very low, low, medium, high or very high, increasing the market potential of the evaluated kit for the given user. This is translated in the allocation of scores from 1 (very low) to 5 (very high). The result is a qualitative histogram: **the cells having on average the highest bars are considered the most promising business models**, so they are worthy of a deeper analysis. Furthermore, to spot relevant combination of solutions, complementary scores can be considered, meaning that the adoption of integrated kits is able to enhance some of the results. The 4 above-mentioned factors will, then, become a more precise **categorization of benefits** specific for each business model analysed (see *Chapter 6*).

Table 3 Matrix matching IDR solutions and users' categories

SUPPLY \ DEMAND		Industrialized passive envelope	Passive and green envelope	Energy and fresh air distribution	Adaptable building management system	Building integrated photovoltaics	Building integrated solar thermal	Smart glazing window
Single Private user				↓				
Collective private user								
Public Social Housing org.				I O C M				
Private Social Housing org.								
Real Estate developers and investors								

D5.2 / Stakeholder-centred value propositions and business models

The matrix has been filled through a survey (see *Annex A.2*) sent to the solution providers of INFINITE kits that evaluated their own solution against all possible User categories. The qualitative histograms obtained are shown in *Table 4*.

Table 4 Qualitative evaluation of different IDR solutions for different user categories

SUPPLY \ DEMAND		Industrialized passive envelope	Passive and green envelope	Energy and fresh air distribution	Adaptable building management system	Building integrated photovoltaics	Building integrated solar thermal	Smart glazing window
Single Private user								
Collective private user								
Public Social Housing org.								
Private Social Housing org.								
Real Estate developers and investors								

I = Incentives availability; O = Payback from OPex savings; C = Savings from CAPEX reduction; M = Recognized

A general overview of the completed matrix shows two main relevant aspects:

- **Industrialized passive envelope** has not a significant recognized market value yet, but incentives are increasing to push deeper interventions. The reason lies in the fact that it implies a high Capex cost and a low return on investment, even though it's a required element to reach a proper level of energy efficiency. Its value can be increased when 2D panels or 3D modules are used to build volumetric extensions on renovated roofs (see *Insight box #3* for further details).
- **Integration with other components is needed** for the Business Model to be sustainable, getting benefits from both energy savings and energy production. The combination with a mechanical ventilation system and a smart window helps improving OPex due to lower heat losses. However, the greatest contribution is given by photovoltaics panels - installed together with an aBMS - which can generate a revenue stream, eventually enhanced by the participation in Renewable Energy Communities (see *Insight box #1* for further details).

6. Business models results

Starting from the matrix results, after specific Partners' interviews (see *Annex A.3*), **three business models have been selected**, with the intent of combining solutions with complementary scores, to enhance the overall value proposition. The business models have different levels of integration, depending on the user category, to explore what are some possible blends that have an actual market potential, even if initial investment costs, degrees of complexity and reached performances are quite dissimilar.

Table 5 Selection of most promising business model

SUPPLY \ DEMAND		Industrialized passive envelope	Passive and green envelope	Energy and fresh air distribution	Adaptable building management system	Building integrated photovoltaics	Building integrated solar thermal	Smart glazing window
Single Private user								
1. Collective private user		✓			✓	✓		✓
2. Public Social Housing org.		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
3. Private Social Housing org.								
Real Estate developers and investors		✓	✓		✓	✓		

The business models can be visualized In *Table 5*: in yellow there are the included INFINITE kits, while in grey the Industrialized passive envelope is highlighted, since it's always needed as substructure to host and integrate the other solutions, both on the roof and façade. In the next paragraphs each case is detailed through a **business model Canvas** (developed through a workshop with all Partners, see *Annex A.3*) and a **list of benefits** to be valorised (still coming from INFINITE Partners' inputs, see *Annex A.4*). More in detail, the three promising cases are:

- **BUSINESS MODEL #1:** Industrialized passive roof with Integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) + smart glazing window and adaptable building management system (aBMS) for Collective private users.
- **BUSINESS MODEL #2:** Industrialized passive envelope with integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) and solar thermal (BIST) + energy and fresh air distribution and adaptable building management system (aBMS) for Public Social Housing organizations.
- **BUSINESS MODEL #3:** Industrialized passive and green envelope with integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) and adaptable building management system (aBMS) for Real Estate developers and investors.

BUSINESS MODEL #1: Collective private users

Industrialized passive roof with Integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) + smart glazing window and adaptable building management system (aBMS)

Starting from the **value proposition**, the combination of smart windows, photovoltaic panels and aBMS generates an interesting model for end users living in collective housing, since it targets private components only, which can be added/changed without the approval of all the homeowners board (compared to interventions such as the roof/façade renewal). However, this is true just for photovoltaics panels that lay on top of the existing roof. If they are integrated in the industrialized passive modules, an agreement between all owners is still needed, because the renovation of the whole roof is involved.

Once the installation of this system takes place, the values for the customers are many. First, there is a generation of energy that provides profit/savings, and it reduces the risk of future rise in energy costs. Furthermore, the aesthetics of the windows are improved, and the overall performances are guaranteed over time, increasing the building financial value. Finally, thanks to the photovoltaic panels, individual powering station for electric vehicles can be provided as well, generating further appeal in the system for the interested residents.

From an **economic point of view**, the main costs come from the initial installation of both windows and PV together with the maintenance and monitoring services over time.

D5.2 / Stakeholder-centred value propositions and business models

Thanks to the inclusion of a building management system, the main **channel** to keep in touch with the customers is the communication of the monitored performances through regular emails/updates showing comfort improvements and periodical comparison between energy generations and consumptions.

Key resources of this system are not only the PV, windows and software technologies but also the shared know-how of the different suppliers, which is essential to provide an integrated and effective service. This implies the involvement of **few key partners** besides the technology suppliers and the installers depending on the type of customer and the related financial model.

Customers can be divided in lower income owners and higher income owners, having different financial needs and means. The ones having a higher level of liquidity can choose to pre-finance the entire initial investment exploiting from day one the revenues coming from the energy generation and bills savings. Another possibility is the involvement of **external investors** (such as ESCOs or Utility companies) to reduce the CAPex. In this model the owners keep paying the same energy bills (adding or not a monthly fee for other services such as maintenance) over an agreed period. The delta savings are taken from the third party to return of the investment and gain operative margin. Usually, Utilities try to be more competitive compared to ESCOs because it is to their benefit to use this financing mechanism to retain their customers.

The business model Canvas is shown in *Figure 3*.

Figure 3 Business model #1 Canvas

MAIN BENEFITS TO BE VALORIZED

The IDR benefits related to Industrialized Deep Renovation that acquire more relevance in this business model are:

- **Increase in property value.** Buildings equipped with sustainable features such as smart windows, PV panels, and advanced aBMS are often perceived as more valuable in the real estate market. These features enhance the building's energy efficiency and appeal to environmentally conscious buyers or tenants, potentially leading to higher property values.
- **Lower energy consumption and bills.** It is the main driver of this model due to reduced heat losses and cleaner energy (electricity) generation. BIPV and aBMS can significantly lower utility expenses without having a too high initial investment cost.
- **Living continuity and less disruptions.** Compared to traditional renovation methods, smart windows can be retrofitted without major structural changes, minimizing the need for construction work and reducing disturbance to occupants. Similarly, PV panels can often be installed on existing roofs without significant alterations to the building's structure. aBMS implementation generally involves integrating new control systems with the existing infrastructure, avoiding extensive modifications.
- **Better indoor comfort.** Smart windows can regulate the amount of natural light and heat entering a building, creating a more comfortable indoor environment. By maintaining optimal temperature and lighting conditions, occupant comfort is improved, leading to higher productivity levels. aBMS allows for precise control of environmental parameters, ensuring a pleasant, healthy and conducive living space for residents.
- **Greater durability.** Smart windows and aBMS offer real-time monitoring capabilities, enabling building managers to track energy consumption, indoor air quality, and system performance. This data can be used to identify and rectify issues promptly, improving operational efficiency and reducing downtime. Additionally, predictive maintenance can be implemented, optimizing equipment lifespan and minimizing repair costs.
- **Revenue generation.** Buildings equipped with PV panels and aBMS can be integrated into smart grid systems. Excess electricity generated by PV panels can be fed into Renewable Energy Communities, earning credits or revenue through net metering or feed-in tariffs. aBMS allows for dynamic load management, enabling buildings to participate in demand response programs, reducing strain on the grid during peak periods.

INSIGHT BOX #1:

Participation in Renewable Energy Communities (REC)

A Renewable Energy Community (REC) is a legally recognized collaborative initiative that enables individuals, households, businesses, and public entities to **jointly produce, share, and consume renewable energy** — typically at the local level. The concept is rooted in EU Directive (2018/2001 – RED II), which aims to **democratize the energy transition**, enhance local resilience and stimulate the direct involvement of communities. Although RECs assume different configurations and regulations according to national contexts, the key principle is the creation of distributed plants for the generation of renewable energy (solar, wind, or biomass) whose production is consumed internally by the members of the community. In this way, the classic distinction between producer and consumer is overcome, introducing the concept of **Prosumer**, that is, a subject who simultaneously produces and uses energy. This community-driven approach not only reduces reliance on traditional energy providers but also fosters a sense of collective responsibility towards environmental sustainability.

RECs enable **virtual self-consumption**: if one member of the REC injects energy into the grid, and another consumes energy at that same moment, both can have economic benefits — even if they're in different apartments or buildings. The energy flow diagram of a CER can be represented through the following scheme:

Figure 4 Scheme of flows within a CER. Translated from the source: *Comunità Energetiche Rinnovabili, KPMG for Friuli-Venezia Giulia*

The REC model is especially attractive for **Collective housing**, where rooftop space is limited but energy sharing can significantly increase the value of generated photovoltaic (PV) electricity, leading to **economic convenience**. **Collective self-consumption** is also a possibility but with a more limited scope: it involves a group of consumers who share the energy produced by a common renewable energy installation (e.g., photovoltaic panels on the roof). The primary focus is on maximizing the self-consumption of the energy generated within the group, reducing the need to draw power externally, so energy trading, demand response, virtual compensation and community-wide planning are not widespread. The main differences are summarized in **Table 6**:

Table 6 Differences between Collective self-consumption and REC

Aspect	Collective self-consumption	Renewable Energy Community (REC)
Scope	Limited to a single building or set of co-located units	Can involve multiple buildings and diverse actors
Governance	Often informal or simplified	Requires legal entity with formal governance (e.g., cooperative or association)
Participants	Typically building co-owners	Can include households, SMEs, municipalities
Incentives	Feed-in tariff or energy bill savings	Incentives for shared energy, sometimes with additional funding or tax benefits
Grid use	Internal use only; no reward for external redistribution	Supports virtual exchange over public grid infrastructure

The main benefits of RECs are:

1. **Cost savings:** By participating in a REC, Collective housing users can significantly reduce their energy bills. The shared production and consumption of renewable energy leads to substantial savings. For instance, a condominium with photovoltaic panels on the roof can save up to **20-30%** on energy bills annually, depending on the national incentive scheme and the degree of self-consumption.
2. **Energy resilience:** RECs reduce reliance on volatile grid energy prices and enhance energy security at the local level — an increasingly important feature amid energy crises or supply disruptions.
3. **Environmental impact:** Utilizing renewable energy reduces greenhouse gas emissions and the community's carbon footprint, contributing to broader climate goals.

4. **Community engagement:** RECs foster a sense of community and collective action. Residents become more aware of their energy consumption patterns and are motivated to adopt sustainable practices.
5. **Regulatory alignment:** With RED II implementation spreading across the EU, many governments offer financial incentives, grants, and subsidies to support the establishment and operation of RECs, making it financially attractive.
6. **Enhanced property value:** Properties that are part of RECs, with guaranteed access to local renewable energy and performance monitoring systems (via aBMS), often enjoy higher market value and faster resale or rental turnover.

On the contrary, the main challenges include:

1. **Upfront investment:** While long-term savings are attractive, initial CAPEX for PV panels, inverters, smart meters, and legal setup can be a barrier. Business models with third-party investors or ESCO participation can mitigate this challenge.
2. **Administrative hurdles:** Navigating the regulatory landscape can be complex. Different countries and regions have varying regulations regarding energy production, distribution, and community energy projects.
3. **Legal complexity:** Establishing a REC typically requires a legal entity and a governance structure. In collective housing, reaching a co-ownership agreement can be complex unless decision thresholds are legally streamlined.
4. **Technical expertise:** Establishing and managing a REC requires technical knowledge and expertise in renewable energy systems, grid management, and energy trading.
5. **Maintenance and management:** Ongoing maintenance of the renewable energy systems and the management of the community's energy needs can be challenging, requiring dedicated resources.
6. **Participation and engagement:** Ensuring active participation and engagement from all community members can be difficult. Furthermore, benefits distribution must be transparent and equitable to keep members involved and committed.

Overall, most EU countries have either fully implemented or are in the process of finalizing the legal frameworks for RECs. The European Commission encourages **pilot initiatives** and **progressive regulations** to foster bottom-up learning before scaling up. This aligns with INFINITE's Renovation 4.0 model, where BIPV installations act as launchpads for REC participation. In addition, aBMS can serve as **technical backbone**, aggregating consumption data, tracking generation, and distributing benefits. In conclusion, RECs can be offered as **service-enhanced packages**, especially for collective housing, transforming a renovation project into a community-scale decarbonization initiative.

BUSINESS MODEL #2: Public Social Housing organizations

Industrialized passive envelope with integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) and solar thermal (BIST) + energy and fresh air distribution and adaptable building management system (aBMS)

Starting from the **value proposition**, the offsite integration of passive façade, photovoltaics, solar thermal and air distribution modules facilitate the renovation process since it improves the efficiency of onsite works, and it reduces the risks of the whole process (delays, errors in the delivery, workplace accidents, etc.). Furthermore, the industrialization allows to optimize the design phase and control the production quality to set reliable guarantees of performances over time.

Talking about warranties, it's important to highlight that a **key resource** to be developed it's a proper installation and maintenance knowledge because the air distribution performances are very dependent on external conditions and on the way the module is connected to the existing building. Furthermore, a strong offsite construction know-how and an adaptation of the façade provider's factory are needed to effectively implement the integration and industrialization of components, which is a key activity.

Another important aspect is the definition of roles and responsibilities of the **different actors involved** and the coordination of the activities. When possible, the proposed model sees the façade provider as the general contractor who offers the integrated component to the social housing organization while BIPV, BIST and air distribution providers are considered as subcontractors, so key partners in the delivery of the overall product.

D5.2 / Stakeholder-centred value propositions and business models

The only possible **channel** through which Public Social Housing organizations can be reached by the integrated façade provider is the call for tenders with all its specific rules and conditions. With the aim of minimizing the whole cost of the renovation, it's better that a specific call is opened to collect the offers related to the envelope integrated modules only. In this way prices can be more competitive compared to a one-stop-shop solution in which is more difficult to check that every work provided is cost-efficient. However, if the public owner has not enough funding to finance the whole CAPEX investment, Public Private Partnerships (PPP) are a recent procurement solution that implies the involvement of a Utility or ESCO company with an Energy Performance Contract (EPC)

Once the intervention is over, as part of the contract, the **relationship** with the Housing organization is kept through the maintenance plan and the monitoring of the building performances over the warranty time. Energy supply is also included in case of EPC or similar models.

From an **economic point of view**, in the first phase, the costs of the intervention can't be included in the value proposition since they are high due to the innovation effort involved. They can be lowered only through a process massification and a proper selection of the building stock to be renovated. In addition, due to the improved energy performances of the envelope, the optimization of the air distribution and the installation of PV panels and aBMS, lower energy bills, maintenance savings and extra-revenues should be considered, together with the improved comfort conditions of the tenants which are a relevant aspect in a social housing environment.

The business model Canvas is shown in *Figure 5*.

Figure 5 Business model #2 Canvas

MAIN BENEFITS TO BE VALORIZED

The IDR benefits related to Industrialized Deep Renovation that acquire more relevance in this business model are:

- **Low energy consumptions and bills.** It's important in all renovations, however, tenants in social housing can't afford high energy bills, so it's an important aspect to be valorised. In this case the split incentive dilemma arises since the public social housing company pays for the renovation and tenants get lower energy bills, so it is crucial to better assess how the owner can get part of revenues from onsite energy production or through little rent increases, if allowed by local laws.
- **Living continuity and shorter intervention time.** It's significant as low-income tenants might be reallocated during traditional renovations. It is a benefit for tenants but also for the owner since no costs or reallocation of existing tenants occur, due to lower disruptions. It could also be a prerequisite in the call for tenders to renovate this type of buildings.
- **Cost certainty and less onsite variations.** It is relevant for this business model given that public entities usually have an annual limited budget, so deviations need an extraordinary approval and represent a bureaucratic burden. However real projects and reliable simulations are needed to get statistical data on retrofitted projects and have valuable estimations on costs.
- **Better indoor comfort.** It is important for social housing tenants who probably do not have private health insurance, and it can really improve their quality of life. However, it is a benefit paid by the owner, unless specific public money is allocated due to the savings recognized to the whole healthcare system.
- **Assembly - disassembly or replicable design processes.** It might be relevant in this model if similar building typologies are owned, which is usually the case for social housing organizations with big stocks to be managed and economies of scale to be created across projects.

INSIGHT BOX #2:

Role of ESCO's intermediation

Public administrations (PA) often face significant financial constraints, making it challenging to fund large-scale building retrofit projects. Traditional financing methods, such as direct budget allocations, can be insufficient to cover the substantial upfront costs associated with buildings' renovation to improve energy efficiency. This financial gap necessitates the exploration of alternative financing mechanisms that can provide the necessary capital without straining public budgets.

Among all the possible alternatives, the most used and spread alternative financing mechanisms are:

- **Public Private Partnerships (PPPs):** these collaborations between government entities and private sector companies can pool resources and expertise to fund and implement retrofit projects that might otherwise be financially unfeasible for public administrations alone.
- **Grants and subsidies:** national and international organizations, such as the European Union, offer grants and subsidies specifically aimed at energy efficiency improvements. These funds do not need to be repaid, making them an attractive option for public administrations.
- **Dedicated energy efficiency funds:** These funds can be established by governments, financial institutions, or through public-private initiatives to support energy-saving initiatives and can be accessed by public administrations to finance retrofit projects.
- **Commercial financing:** Banks and private investors can provide loans or issue bonds to finance retrofit projects, often at favourable terms due to the long-term energy savings expected.

The most effective strategy to overcome the barrier of high initial investment is to leverage **Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) and Energy Performance Contracts (EPCs)**. These mechanisms allow public administrations to undertake retrofit projects without the need for substantial upfront capital. This financing mechanism could work also coupled with the alternatives listed above, maximizing the benefit for the public administration.

Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) are specialized companies that provide comprehensive energy solutions, including the design, implementation, and financing of energy efficiency projects. ESCOs typically guarantee energy savings, and their remuneration is directly tied to the performance of the implemented measures. The development of ESCo companies had a boost in Europe thanks to the Energy Efficiency Directive (Directive 2012/27/EU), which promoted the use of Energy Performance Contracts (EPCs) across the European Union.

In fact, one of the main contracting tools used by ESCo is the **Energy Performance Contract (EPC)**, that is an agreement between a building owner and an ESCo, where the latter undertakes the retrofit project and guarantees a certain level of

energy savings. This model transfers technical and financial risks to the ESCo, ensuring that the project delivers the promised performances, needed to pay back the renovation investment. EPC contracts are multi-years contracts that involve also the **maintenance service** and the **energy supply**, allowing the building owner to have a unique supply contract with the ESCo company (see **Figure 6**). The mechanism considers that the building owner pays to the ESCo company an **annual fee** that is approximatively equal to the costs for energy and maintenance paid before the retrofit intervention, hence the ESCo covers the investment with the guaranteed savings.

Figure 6 Services included in the EPC contract

The involvement of an intermediary company as the ESCo and leveraging an EPC contract changes the business model of the intervention (see **Figure 7**).

Figure 7 Business model with ESCo and EPC contract

The use of this business model allows the public administration to benefit from several advantages, beside the financial one. From a more technical perspective, this business model allows to simplify the process for the public administration, having the ESCo as a single point of accountability, that manage the entire project from design to implementation and maintenance. Finally, the ESCo brings specialized **technical expertise** to the project, ensuring that the most effective energy efficiency measures are implemented. This is a significant benefit for public administrations that usually do not have the internal knowhow required for such projects.

Considering a residential building owned by a public administration where is performed an energy retrofit with IDR solutions it is possible to perform a **qualitative economical comparison** between a traditional business model and an ESCo business model. The hypothesis is to perform a retrofit that leads to an overall reduction of the energy cost of approximately 50%, for a total investment of around € 1 million for a medium-sized building. Without involving an ESCo the owner should overcome the initial CAPex through its own liquidity or asking for private debt at an average interest rate that depends on the national contexts. On the contrary, considering the involvement of an ESCo and an EPC contract of the duration, hypothetically, of 10 years, the ESCo covers the whole investment, and the public administration has to repay the ESCo with an annual fee. At the end of the contract, this financing mechanism will result in an extra cost for the PA that ranges from **10 to 20%** compared to the scenario where the full amount of CAPex is available from the first year. Of course, the value of the extra cost depends on the financing conditions, the profit of the ESCo, the duration of the contract and the services included in it. Overall, even if the EPC implies an additional expense over time, it's a model that is spreading rapidly because it enables interventions that otherwise cannot occur and for which bank loans are not always possible or more convenient than the ESCO's intermediation.

BUSINESS MODEL #3: Real Estate developers and investors

Industrialized passive and green envelope with integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) and adaptable building management system (aBMS)

The combination of green envelope kits for façade and roof along with BIPV panels connected to a dedicated aBMS is a design solution which appear to add **high value** to the building, in particular when referring to Real estate funds, who are willing to differentiate their offer with more interesting and sustainable solutions, by simultaneously enhancing their “green image”. The key advantage, in that sense, is the visibility of the components installed, which improve visual identity and market attractiveness with low marketing actions related to the regeneration project realized (see as reference the famous Bosco Verticale by Stefano Boeri Architetti in Milan).

A **key partner** for Real Estate funds is the facility management company, which would be appointed for the maintenance and operational activities involved in running the building after its refurbishment, especially to preserve the green elements. In addition, recent years have seen a governmental shift towards supporting design choices directed at reducing the risk of climate change on the built environment, with reference to flood risk mitigation measures as well as heat island effects reduction in dense cities. Within this context, the green kit offers a compelling way to tackle such challenges, therefore Governance bodies and policy makers represent key partners in supporting the uptake and implementation of such solutions. Within the potential partners grid managers and ESCO’s can also see benefits arising from the implementation of the BIPV façade and roof system, which facilitate Local energy generation and net metering.

D5.2 / Stakeholder-centred value propositions and business models

Activities that can boost the uptake of the integration of BIPV and green kits from Real Estate funds include the implementation of more regulatory measures, incentives from governance, engagement activities and showcase of technologies through pilots' projects, quality insurance and warranties for managing such Innovative investments.

The **knowledge** necessary to trigger this model is to be found and upscaled among the manufacturers and installers of the kits, as well as the climate experts which can perform simulations of solar radiation and impact on urban heat islands studies, to show the added benefit for the building and for the neighbourhood (further proved by the aBMS monitoring). Upskilling training is also required for design, engineering and installation companies to work with such innovative systems.

From an **economic perspective**, these components not only improve sustainability but also support value creation through increased rents, higher asset valuations, and alignment with ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) investment frameworks and green certification schemes (e.g., LEED, BREEAM). While the initial investment is significant, the multi-layered returns make it attractive for long-term asset holders, especially when combined with green financing tools (e.g. green bonds, ESG loans).

The business model Canvas is shown in *Figure 8*.

Figure 8 Business model #3 Canvas

MAIN BENEFITS TO BE VALORIZED

The IDR benefits related to Industrialized Deep Renovation that acquire more relevance in this business model are:

- **Increase in property value.** It is a crucial driver for Real Estate Funds, but the extra value may vary significantly depending on the location, market demand, and specific characteristics of the property.
- **Lower energy consumptions and bills.** It is to be considered since green roofs provide insulation, reducing the need for heating and cooling systems. Furthermore, by generating renewable energy onsite, property owners can reduce their dependence on conventional power sources and lower their energy bills. Also, decreased energy consumption makes the property more attractive to potential buyers or tenants.
- **Better indoor comfort and health.** It is mainly related to acoustic insulation and noise reduction. Indeed, green roofs act as effective sound insulators, reducing noise pollution from the surrounding environment. This can be particularly beneficial for properties located in urban areas or near neuralgic infrastructures.
- **Better architectural quality.** It is relevant for this model because green envelopes add visual appeal to buildings, especially in dense built environments where green space is limited. They provide a natural and inviting atmosphere, contributing to a sense of calmness and well-being. Aesthetically pleasing properties are often more desirable and can command higher prices.
- **Lower emissions and environmental impact.** Green roofs contribute to carbon dioxide reduction, help manage stormwater runoff, and support biodiversity by providing habitats for plants and animals. Buyers and tenants increasingly value eco-friendly features, but mainly in premium markets.
- **Better financial and insurance conditions.** It is applicable only where regulatory incentives are present. Indeed, in some regions, there may be tax benefits (credits, grants, or expedited permit processing) for properties that incorporate green features. Taking advantage of such programs provides potential financial benefits for the owner.

INSIGHT BOX #3:

Volumetric extensions for existing roofs

Context & Rationale

Volumetric extensions — defined as the addition of new modular prefabricated space to an existing building footprint (e.g., vertical rooftop extensions or horizontal protrusions) — represent an underexplored yet high-potential renovation avenue within the framework of Renovation 4.0. In the context of INFINITE, these extensions can integrate green façades, BIPV, ventilation and industrialised envelope kits, enhancing both usable floor space and property value while maintaining strong alignment with sustainability and resilience goals. Particularly for Real Estate Funds, this solution can unlock new revenue streams via space densification, premium rents and environmental stewardship.

Figure 9 Example of serial roof raising. Source: RoofUz

Strategic Benefits

1. **Property value uplift:** Volumetric extensions not only modernize appearance but create new functional areas (e.g., rooftop apartments or offices) with high rental or sale potential. According to studies in dense urban areas (e.g. Berlin, Paris), rooftop extensions can increase property values by **10–25%**, especially when combined with green architecture and PV systems.
2. **Climate resilience and urban cooling:** Green roof and wall installed on volumetric extensions help mitigate urban heat island effects and provide added insulation. They represent a compact and circular use of space with double climate impact, reducing operational emissions and improving microclimate.

3. **High market differentiation:** Real estate investors increasingly seek projects with sustainability labels and regenerative design features. Volumetric extensions built with prefabricated green envelopes and active solar systems can serve as flagship developments, particularly in LEED, BREEAM certification contexts, in line with the requirements of the EU taxonomy.
4. **Scalable business case:** INFINITE Slovenian demo case demonstrates the feasibility of offsite renovation and roof raising. Compared with equivalent typologies undergoing traditional retrofits, it provides:
 - Measured OPex benefits through energy-efficient offsite modules
 - Shorter construction times
 - Minimized disruption, thanks to plug-and-play architecture

In practice, the volumetric extension is a module that can easily embed green envelope, ventilation, BIPV tech and façade insulation methods, being a valuable and convenient way to integrate IDR solutions with respect to more traditional floor raising (see **Table 6**).

Table 6 Comparison among traditional and offsite extensions

Aspect	Traditional extension	Green offsite extension
Design and permits	Custom-designed, high engineering load	Modular, pre-approved lower effort
Construction time	8–12 months (average)	4–6 weeks offsite, 1–2 weeks onsite
Energy efficiency	Often neglected or passive only	Passive + active BIPV systems
Value addition	Medium (related to additional floor area)	High, dual functional (green + usable)
Disruption	High (tenant relocation often needed)	Medium (non-invasive installation)

Integration requirements

Overall, volumetric extensions are an effective way to enhance renovation business models, but it's important to keep in mind that their feasibility must be checked against a list of requirements:

- **Urban planning compatibility.** Alignment with height limits and zoning can be a strong constraint in term of extra volume available
- **Structural assessments.** Load-bearing capacity and seismic conditions of the existing building must be pre-verified.
- **Utility upgrades.** Heating electrical and hydraulic integration into existing systems should be properly designed.

7. Further developments

This report has laid a **foundational framework** for understanding and designing business models tailored to Industrialized Deep Renovation (IDR) beside the INFINITE project scope and according to the innovative solutions available, from time to time, on the market. The strategic evaluations provided can help shaping how IDR can be commercially and operationally scaled across European countries.

However, the analysis remains **primarily qualitative**. While the document identifies valuable synergies between technologies, stakeholders Involved and business models, it does not delve into detailed financial metrics, performance data or cost comparisons. As such, this work should be seen as an essential but preliminary step in business model development, lacking economic evaluation.

The next phase of development will be tackled in the public Deliverable *D6.9 (Evaluation of INFINITE results implementation)* which will conduct **quantitative assessments** of the identified models in real-world contexts, specifically, the INFINITE demo cases in France, Italy, and Slovenia. This forthcoming analysis will include financial analysis of CAPex, OPex, available incentives, rental impacts, and other monetized benefits. Importantly, D6.9 will compare IDR solutions with **traditional renovation** approaches applied to the same buildings, allowing a clearer understanding of the economic (e.g. LCC, Return on Investment, breakeven) practical (e.g. works duration, durability, users' satisfaction) and environmental (e.g. LCA, DfAD, circularity) implications of industrialized renovation, explored under multiple financing schemes.

Overall, while this document provides a strategic vision and conceptual grounding, its limitations - particularly the lack of numerical data and application in live settings - highlight the importance of a **continued development** to validate and refine the IDR business models in practice.

Annex

All the outputs of the present report have been elaborated through a series of activities which involved different INFINITE Partners. More in detail, the following actions have been undertaken:

- **Online workshop** with the goal of better characterize and validate the matrix (see paragraph A.1).
- **Survey distribution** aiming at filling out the matrix to select the three most promising business models (see paragraph A.2).
- **Interviews and in-person workshop** to characterize the Canvas of the three selected business models (see paragraph A.3).
- **Final workshop** aiming at identifying the relevant benefits connected to each business model with respect to more traditional approaches (see paragraph A.4).

A.1 Matrix validation, online workshop

In March 2022 it has been held an online workshop among WP5 Partners with the support of a Miro Board (see *Figure 10*), to brainstorm about the stakeholder categories and the IDR solutions and to validate the overall demand-supply matrix structure.

Figure 10 Miro Board used to validate the matrix

D5.2 / Stakeholder-centred value propositions and business models

The main activities have been:

- listing all general PROs and CONs of all technological solutions
- citing the main renovation needs of all the stakeholders (both final users and Intermediaries)

Furthermore, in the internal workshop it emerged that the cell qualitative assessment should be carried out by the INFINITE kit producers (and not by WP5 Partners) because they could provide a more knowledgeable point of view, being the main players in the reference market.

A.2 Survey distribution, offline compilation

After the online workshop, a survey for the kit producers was created and distributed. The objective was the compilation of the matrix cells through the evaluation of how IDR solutions can be differently valorised by each stakeholder category which have different needs, scope and budget.

An extract of the survey distributed to the solution providers is shown in **Figure 11**. The whole survey, instead, is available at the following link: <https://forms.gle/K22AndemAi8nxuX86>. Results from each answer have been aggregated and are shown in the filled matrix in **Table 4**.

For each of the following stakeholder categories assign a score from Very Low to Very high according to the presence level of the 4 business model factors. Results will be analyzed to provide qualitative diagrams as the one below

Very high	High	Medium	Low	Very low
	High			
		Medium		
			Low	
				Very low

What is the Renovation 4.0 solution you are working on?

- Industrialized passive envelope
- Green envelope
- Integrated energy generation and distribution
- Smart glazing-shading window
- Building integrated photovoltaics BIPV
- Building integrated solar thermal BIST
- Building Management System BMS

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high
Incentives availability	<input type="radio"/>				
Payback from OPex savings	<input type="radio"/>				
Savings from CAPex reduction	<input type="radio"/>				
Recognized market value	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments (if any) about the scores assigned to SINGLE PRIVATE USERS
E.g. any kit integration that could increase the given scores or any particular adoption barriers/incentives

La tua risposta

Figure 11 Miro Board used to validate the matrix

A.3 Partners interviews and Canvas definition, in-person activities

In May 2022, during the third project meeting in Ljubljana, a couple of activities has been organized to start a preliminary discussion on the business models definition and get useful insights from the Partners. In particular:

- Few interviews were planned to provide some instructions explaining the matrix goal and get some feedback.
- According to the information emerged from the interviews, 3 business models have been highlighted.
- Such models have been discussed during a 45-minutes working session with the Partner divided into 3 groups. Each group was given an empty Canvas to be filled up according to the assigned case.

Starting from the interviews, some general considerations from each Partner have been spotted:

- **Vortice** energy generation and distribution kit is designed to be integrated in the façade so it must be conveyed by the envelope supplier. The innovation lies in the combination of both air and heat exchange to improve the indoor comfort. The most reasonable customer segment is not condominiums since it's hard to convince all the owners to change their technical plants. Social housing organizations, on the contrary, are more sensitive to management costs savings and they can assure their tenants that the intervention will provide them with significant benefits and improved living conditions. Single-family houses can be a valid target as well because they have only one ownership. Furthermore, for small building this type of kit can also integrate the heat generation, being even more compact and innovative.
- **Rubner** is not developing a new specific kit or solution since the innovation is based on the way the envelope is integrated with all the other kits (BIST, BIPV, smart window, VMC and aBMS sensors). The level of integration to be reached has an impact on the commercial strategies, the needed certifications (to respect regulation standards and guaranteed performances) and the potential for applicability (fully prefabricated modules are less versatile compared to single kits which can be applied to a broader range of building typologies). For the integration to be truly effective, the business model should start from a clear definition of the needs coming from the demand: what are the willing to pay for, the level of comfort and aesthetics, the possibility to hide technical plants, the maintenance costs, etc.). As a second step, all the solution providers can find the most effective way to combine the different kits focusing on the scope of responsibility and the overall performance warranties. In the eyes of the customer, there should be one only point of reference, reachable through the definition of a new certified integrated product and the adoption of the one-shop-model.
- **Sunage** photovoltaic panels are already on the market, so the innovation brought by Infinite project lies in the integration with the prefabricated envelope (roof and façade) and the Building Management system. For instance, understanding what changes need to be done to match the other kits is important since any variation implies new tests to get new certifications that prove the consistency with the external conditions. One of the main characteristics of the panels is the variety of coloured finishings so customers are generally looking for esthetical performances, besides the energetic ones. Therefore, the target is high, excluding Social Housing Organizations and One Stop Shops which usually seek more economically advantageous solutions.

- **Casa Spa**, being a social housing organization, represents the demand point of view. The proposal which better satisfy their retrofit needs is the integrated solution. Indeed, one of their priorities is to properly identify the building clusters that optimize the integration of certain kits compared to others. In general, due to their social nature, all the interventions must be economically sustainable so a return on the investment must be guaranteed, through the setup of proper performance warranties. Furthermore, in public housing the energy bills are charged to the tenants so SHOs can't get any gain from Open savings (besides reaching the goal of reducing energy poverty). However, if the intervention is assigned to an energy provider which can exploit the bills reduction to return of part of its investment, SHOs can reduce their Capex expenditure.
- **Grunstattgrau's** experience shows that the green roofs can reduce the urban heat-island effect produced by solar panels, improving their performances. The combination of the two kits results, then, in a win-win solution. However, due to the high costs of green modules, their implementation on private condominiums and social housing buildings is highly improbable. Real Estate entities, instead, can usually afford higher capex investments because the increased market value and the aesthetical/environmental improvements provided to the urban contest, generate profitable paybacks.
- **Physee** sensors are adding innovative potential to the smart window kit since currently there are no options that really measures the solar radiation on the different facades (usually there is only one sensor on top of the building). The main target are buildings having high glass ratios (like offices or new high-rise apartments) because the right scale is needed, due to the high cost of the gateway. The integration with the aBMS data coming from the ventilation system could also add value since having under control the whole climate system allows a more appropriate regulation of the sun shadings. The actual business model is based on low Capex cost of the hardware for the building owner and significant OPex costs related to the service provided and paid by the tenants through a subscription proportional to the apartment area.
- According to **Bouygues**, the aBMS system has so far low market uptake, especially when considered on its own as a standalone version connected to sensors. With the INFINITE kits it shows an improvement in its market appeal. The customer targets of the aBMS system are new developments, with a focus on social housing owners and collective private users /condominium complex, the latter being a future target though. The role of the aBMS provider can be seen as an intermediary between the demand sector and the supply sector that can satisfy a variety of stakeholders. For instance, a new product launched by Bouygues called SMALT has seen success thanks to a sort of dedicated new offer that matched specific stakeholders demand for indoor control and digitalization. A combination of IoT system with the sensors and the aBMS system has potential for high market uptake, due to the versatility to adapt the user experience thanks to the digital data services, for instance by connecting the aBMS to parking services, registering access to the building along with the building performance management and optimization. In France the private owners and the targeted customer segments are still not aware of the opportunities, therefore engagement and awareness campaign is crucial to see changes in this sector. Ultimately, the aBMS kit can add real value when most or all the kits are integrated in the building, than the solution is appealing, the payback is good, the premise is future proof and the monthly expenses are reduced.

After the workshop activity, each group took 5 minutes to present the related business model Canvas as summarized in *Figure 12*.

D5.2 / Stakeholder-centred value propositions and business models

Figure 12 Canvas filled out during the workshop In Ljubljana

A.4 Benefits selection, in-person activity

In May 2023, during the project meeting in Paris, a working session has been organized to list and discuss the benefits strictly related to Industrialized Deep Renovation which are not relevant enough if traditional retrofits are considered. **Table 6** was distributed to WP5 Partners, and it was filled up for each of the three business models.

Table 6 Comparison among traditional and offsite extensions

BUSINESS MODEL N° ...				
LIST OF BENEFITS	Is the benefit relevant in this BM? why?	What category of stakeholder gets the benefit? Who pay for it?	Can it already be valorised in a BM? How?	Notes, Challenges
Increase in property value (kept over time)				
Lower energy consumption/bills				
Living continuity/less disruptions				
Better indoor comfort/health				
Better quality (also architectural)				
Cost certainty/ less onsite variations				
Shorter and more certain intervention time				

D5.2 / Stakeholder-centred value propositions and business models

Long-term performance warranties				
Greater durability/lower maintenance				
Better working conditions/increased safety				
Lower emissions/environmental impact				
Better financial/insurance conditions				
Integrability of the anti-seismic retrofit				
OTHER				
ex. circularity, dismountability				
ex. accessibility, outdoor spaces				

The most appropriate advantages for every case are reported in paragraph 6, after each Business Model Canvas. The economic valorisation of such benefits will instead be address in Deliverable D6.9 (*Evaluation of INFINITE results implementation*) where quantitative analysis are carried out.